

Incorporating Topology on GPT-Based Geoparsing Model for Finer Geocoding Locations from Social Media Texts

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Summary

The unstructured nature of social media remains a challenge for extracting geographical information from texts. This paper discusses how a Generative Pretrained Transformer (GPT) can extract spatial information from social media texts. The preliminary results indicate that using toponym-based GPT solely to geoparse locational information yields vague, multiple-mentioned locations that cannot be geocoded. This research works toward the incorporation of topology to improve the accuracy of geoparsing and geocoding locations from social media texts.

KEYWORDS: GPT, Geoparsing, Geocoding, Social Media

1. Introduction

In disaster impact assessment, most studies have utilised traditional Natural Language Processing (NLP) to examine the areas of victims and incidents from social media hashtags (Rosser et al., 2017). However, hashtags are often repeated across many posts and mention common place names, such as county names, rather than specific locations as detailed in post texts. As NLP evolves to Large Language Models (LLMs), harnessing social media information is no longer limited to classifying texts into disaster impacts (e.g., physical damage, affected population), filtering informative from uninformative content, and extracting locations from hashtags (Madichetty et al., 2023). Instead, it has extended to extracting written locations within the text. These approaches split texts into multiple entities and assign a label to each to detect which entity is a location and to understand its contextual meaning simultaneously (Suwaileh et al., 2022). In earlier LLM development, the models still relied heavily on large amounts of pre-training data to recognise place names associated with global or higher-level administrative units.

To address this issue, some studies incorporated a gazetteer as a reference for toponym matching to provide more detailed location specification (Karimzadeh et al., 2019). A gazetteer is a collection of toponyms with their coordinates, administrative units, feature types, and population numbers (Karimzadeh et al., 2019). Following NLP developments, recent research has increasingly focused on geoparsing. Geo-parsing aims to identify locational information in text corpora before positioning the locations within a spatial extent. For example, a previous study proposed a geocoding method that corrects the area contained in the text using a preference rank model based on the similarity of tweet toponyms (Zhang & Gelernter, 2014). They utilised a gazetteer as a reference before eliminating candidate names, and then geocoded the corrected names. They highlighted that extracting information from tweets was challenging due to the highly personalised nature of the text, such as writing location

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names with the abbreviation *'Tornado Watch #487 in effect until midnight. #mnwx #ndwx #sdwx.'*

A more promising approach was recently proposed by (X. Hu et al., 2024; Y. Hu et al., 2023) by implementing various Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT)-based models via prompt design to detect and classify locations in text, thereby evaluating GPT's performance in geo-parsing tasks. Y. Hu et al. (2023) extracted place names and assigned predefined classes only, without locating them on the spatial extent, while X. Hu et al. (2024) identified locations and located them, but overlooked the validity and correctness of the spatial footprints.

Although significant progress has been made in extracting place names from social media texts, most existing approaches are limited to name recognition and categorisation, without addressing spatial accuracy, contextual relationships, or validating the resulting locations. It highlights the need for a more integrated analysis that combines advanced language models with robust spatial reasoning and geocoding techniques.

2. Methodology

This research aims to incorporate topological concepts into prompt design to improve LLM performance at recognising locational information in texts. This paper still presents the preliminary experiment of using GPT3.5 architecture and tests on the Hurricane Harvey dataset from <https://crisisnlp.qcri.org/>, comprising 3992 labelled tweets (Alam et al., 2018). In the initial stage of prompt development, this study provides geographical knowledge into GPT as a geoparsing model to classify texts into defined categories (see **Figure 1**). This stage will evaluate whether the previous approach by Y. Hu et al. (2023) is adaptable to this research dataset and identifies its limitations to further develop the prompt design.

```
Prompt
= f"""You are a geolocation classification assistant. Read the tweet carefully and assign it to
exactly ONE of the following location categories based on the type of location mentioned.
C1 = Door number addresses
C2 = Street names
C3 = Highways
C4 = Exits of highways
C5 = Intersections of roads or rivers
C6 = Natural features
C7 = Other human-made features
C8 = Local organizations
C9 = Administrative units
C10 = Multiple areas
C11 = Road segments
Tweet: {text}
Return your answer in JSON format only:{{ "category": "C#", "location_name": "the location
text to geocode", "reason": "brief explanation"}}
```

Figure 1 Geographical knowledge GPT prompt

GPT identifies locations based on these categories and provides reasons for assigning each piece of text to its class, enabling evaluation and interpretation of typical errors. Otherwise, GPT will assign NULL to texts that do not mention any placenames. After the geoparsing process, this research geocodes locations using Nominatim, an OpenStreetMap (OSM)-based geocoding service, to analyse their distribution. The JSON output structure was not designed to align with Nominatim's structured query mode. However, they were entered as free-text strings and geocoded using Nominatim's free-text search. Free-text search enables evaluation of the model's raw output, whereas structured queries can enhance performance through hierarchical constraints. Furthermore, this research validates the positional accuracy of each location using the haversine distance calculation, with Google Maps as the reference dataset. Before the distance-error analysis, reverse geocoding on Google Maps was performed to obtain geographic coordinates for location name outputs. The resulting coordinate pairs, representing the predicted and reference locations, were then used to calculate the cumulative percentage of distance errors.

3. Preliminary result

In the initial stage, this study detects 2062 geoparsed locations from the dataset. **Figure 2** depicts the distribution, showing that many geolocated points are outside the study area. In fact, Hurricane Harvey made landfall around Rockport and caused severe flooding across southeastern Texas, particularly in Houston, with additional impacts in southwestern Louisiana, United States. Therefore, it highlights the need to further refine the prompt to guide GPT more specifically and to provide context rather than solely relying on geographical knowledge.

Figure 2 Geographical knowledge GPT geocoding visualisation

Figure 3 shows that OSM geocoding accuracy increases significantly beyond 15 km. Then, this study examines the geoparsed texts and coordinates extracted from the OSM. It demonstrates that GPT successfully geoparse texts across multiple categories, including door numbers, street names, highway exits, and various areas (see **Figure 4**). However, this work found that OSM cannot locate multiple locations, as seen in the C4 class, indicating that the place name is not recorded in the OSM geodatabase. It concludes that OSM fails to locate detailed locations on the map, resulting in low model accuracy.

Figure 3 Cumulative Percentage of Distance Errors

Input tweets	Geoparsing	Geocoding Address
RT @HillcrestAnston: Excellent Platform 9 3/4 jigsaw Harvey. A great home learning project!!! 6D1B6D1B6D1B https://t.co/rmFihMiRBm	C1 : Platform 9 3/4	C1: Platform 9 3/4, Bell County, Texas, 76559, United States of America
RT @AlexTforTexas: Latest donation needs at the #Harvey Relief Hub (2500 Summer St): https://t.co/gzbVT3GDIL	C2 : 2500 Summer St	C2: 2500, Summer Street, Washington Avenue Coalition / Memorial Park, Houston, Harris County, Texas, 77007, United States of America
1.7 million litres of petrol spill near Houston due to Hurricane Harvey flooding https://t.co/dGUJaDSRfN https://t.co/B9XJzlmur0	C3 : Houston	C3: Houston, Harris County, Texas, United States of America
RT @Allen_Reid: 59 south shut down at first Wharton exit . Cars have to exit and go back to north 59. #Harvey @kprc2 https://t.co/RPV4lklkyQ	C4 : first Wharton exit	NULL
Cowboys 1st & amp; 10: Helping With Harvey, Cutting To 53, Zeke Leak #Bucs https://t.co/2E86a3G16j https://t.co/lqa2xarNgi	C5 : Cowboys	C5: Cowboys, Colinas Monte y Mar, Barrio Pueblo, Rincón, Puerto Rico, 00677, United States of America
Beautiful sunset on Aransas Bay . Our work on Harvey is done. Headed home to enjoy a 8th grade football game. https://t.co/kBG6O3NhHx	C6 : Aransas Bay	C6: Aransas Bay, Rockport, Aransas County, Texas, United States of America
Visit Our 2017 Showcase Home and Help Military Heroes Affected by Harvey https://t.co/RB1GZD96ia	C7 : Showcase Home	C7: Showcase Home Builders., 1193A, Massachusetts Avenue, Arlington Heights, Arlington, Middlesex County, Massachusetts, 02476, United States of America
Italian Club raises funds for Harvey Relief Fund https://t.co/PjUtN95ntr https://t.co/u5S3T9MiWs	C8 : Italian Club	C8: Italian Club, 2148, Connaught Street, Pioneer Village, Regina, Saskatchewan, S4T 1R1, Canada
#Hurricane #Harvey transposed over #Illinois to show widespread #heavyrain @watersurvey https://t.co/c2MPmx1H8 https://t.co/xFVJ8G5IXt	C9 : Illinois	C9: Illinois, United States of America
Tornado Watch #487 in effect until midnight. #mnwx #ndwx #sdwx https://t.co/GlqT28MhQw	C10: Minnesota, North Dakota, South Dakota	NULL
Harvey looks to slow Cubs in 3rd start off DL https://t.co/EdYR7o4lgM #mlb #mets #baseball https://t.co/LmfVxaRSmR	C11: 3rd start off DL	NULL

Figure 4 Geoparsing and Geocoding Result Examples

4. Next Steps

This experiment still overlooks contextual descriptions in the prompt. As a result, the ambiguous place names are being identified. It also overlooks tweets with multiple locations, leading to incomplete geocoding. This demonstrates that although GPT performs well in geoparsing, some multiple-location mentions fail to geocode correctly, and relative or descriptive locations remain mislocated. Traditional geoparsing systems typically combine rule-based named-entity recognition with gazetteer lookups (e.g., GeoNames) as a baseline approach. Therefore, future work will include a quantitative comparison with gazetteer-driven methods to evaluate relative improvements in extraction accuracy and distance error. Additionally, this research will incorporate topological information, such as containment, adjacency, and directional relations, into GPT training to reduce geocoding distance errors and improve spatial accuracy. Finally, Google Maps will be explored as an alternative geocoding service to OpenStreetMap for locating generated place names.

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